

THE RESULTS OBTAINED BY VARIOUS METHODS IN TRADITIONAL SURGICAL PRACTICE AND THE USE OF OPTIMAL SUTURE MATERIALS

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Relevance. The problem under consideration is that the frequency of purulent-septic complications after emergency surgeries is 23.5-71.2%, while in planned surgeries this figure is 0.29%-30%. This situation is described as follows: in emergency surgical pathology, patients often experience symptoms of intoxication, which in turn is due to the fact that the body's protective function is in a decompensated state. It should also be noted that emergency surgeries are performed under conditions of high contamination of organs and tissues, as well as in the group of "conditionally dirty" and "dirty" surgeries, with a high risk of post-diagnostic purulent complications.

The aim of the study. To study the results obtained by various methods in traditional surgical practice using optimal suture materials.

Material and methods of the study. This study is based on the results of surgical treatment of 481 (100.0%) patients with various pathologies of the abdominal organs who were treated in the surgical department of the Andijan Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center in 2020-2023.

Treatment results. Good results of abdominal surgeries were observed in small and large areas. Good immediate results in small and large surgical interventions were observed in 141 (71.6%) of 197 patients. In large areas, this figure was only 58 (29.4%). Negative results were observed in 44 patients in 59.1% of large-field surgeries. This can be explained as follows. As mentioned above, large-scale surgeries are directly related not only to the cavity or parenchymatous organ and tissue, but also to the thickness of the suture material used, its effect on tissue, restoration of intestinal peristalsis, and regeneration of the intestinal loop. Remote results of surgical interventions performed for pathology of the abdominal organs were determined after 6-12 months by reorganizing the patient's visit to the clinic.

Conclusion. The results of the study showed that traditional absorbable polyfilaments increase the number of positive results without side effects on the surrounding healthy tissue in small, medium and large surgical procedures. Although the polyfilaments used in traditional surgical practice have several

advantages, we considered it necessary to improve the use of polyfilaments and develop new ones due to high complications in remote results.

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